

ANALYSIS ON SHORT INTENSIVE PRACTICE ON INTERPRETER TRAINEES' PERFORMANCE

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Abstract: This article reviews and evaluates the topics of an entrance examination created for potential interpreter trainees based on answers from test-takers and trainers. A number of research have examined construct validity in interpretation testing (e.g., Clifford, 2005; Lee, 2008; Eyckmans et al., 2009; Turner et al., 2010), but few have examined the substance of admission exams that decide trainee selection. This article focuses on the psychometric category of authenticity among the methods available for test evaluation, that is, the link between test contents and the elicitation of skill performance during the test are those abilities that were the subject of post-test training.

Keywords: review, subject, post-test training, native speakers, entrance exam, fluent, admission, interpreting.

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Introduction:

The effort was aimed at native speakers of new and developing languages. Other language speakers, however, may take the entrance exam and be considered for admission in the course. Individuals eligible to apply for the programme were expected to be fluent in at least two spoken languages, but no expertise in interpreting or translating was necessary, nor was a specific formal training or a certain degree of schooling required. Because there were no formal qualifications, the programme began with an intake test to assess potential trainees. The exam was meant to extract particular information about the testees' educational and occupational profiles, and it contained activities and questions to assess English language level, general ability, and interest in interpreting. Rather than just documenting learning of linguistic forms or grammatical structures as standard language tests do, this intake exam assessed abilities utilising competency- and function-based techniques. Such functionally oriented testing, i.e. testing to evaluate if a testee can accomplish a specific task using any linguistic form relevant to the task, regardless of complexity, is currently a prevalent strategy in the evaluation of language-focused courses in adult vocational education in Australia. Both second-language acquisition assessment and language and literacy training for first-language speakers have tailored their curriculum and assessment tasks to a

specific circumstance or setting. The usefulness of the intake test in the context of training is determined by how well it elicits individuals' functional capacities.

To investigate the use of the intake exam, we first detail the components of existing tests and test materials created for potential and targeted community interpreting trainees. We next go into the test's design and how each portion was administered to and completed by testees. Through a requirements analysis, we defined the content and pedagogical method for the training based on testee performance. Finally, we assessed the "authenticity" or "validity" of this intake test—its potential to generate answers important to interpretation training and to allow diagnosis of capacities and proficiencies—using evaluative comments from both trainers and trainees. We conclude with a comparison and summary of findings.

In the very small body of research on community interpreter training, the examination of potential applicants has received little attention. The majority of research on interpreting training concentrate on the testing criteria for specialised, high-level courses, many of which are two years long and postgraduate, and often teach students for simultaneous or conference interpreting. Lotriet (2002) presented the aspects of an admission examination for a group of possible trainees for a one-month intensive course in simultaneous interpretation. This exam comprised diagnostic tasks for both languages, as well as additional elements such as the individual's reading habits, personal interests, handling of problematic subjects, and self-concept, all of which were deemed to be essential for the form and content of future assignments.

The International Council for the Development of Community Interpreting (Critical Link) has lately encouraged research into community interpreting training and admission testing. Papers from Critical Link conferences have addressed challenges related to the testing requirements discussed in this page. Straker and Watts (2003), for example, examined educating students from refugee backgrounds, many of whom speak languages unfamiliar to their new home; the authors also emphasised the "activist" aspect of such training for disadvantaged populations. Michael and Cocchini (1997) focused on the emancipatory and empowering impacts of educating young adult bilinguals and establishing them as employed interpreters in their local communities, within language communities that they are familiar with.

There have been few research on the features of intake testing for community interpreter training. According to Mikkelsen and Mintz (1997), addressing ethical questions is as crucial a starting point as measuring English-language competence. Corsellis (2008) stated that low-level training tests should include short role plays, sight translations, brief writing translations, and free written compositions in both

languages that explore the applicant's objectives. Gentile, Ozolins, and Vasilakakos (1996) also proposed a comprehensive list of features to test general language skills with a focus on listening and speaking, knowledge of cultural mores within each language community, basic note-taking techniques, memory retention exercises, and professional ethics.

Of course, an entrance exam may include questions and exercises to assess the applicant's knowledge of discourse-pragmatic norms, topic- and domain-specific terminology; skill level in voice modulation (i.e., enunciation in the L1, pronunciation in the L2), handling or establishing turn-taking conventions, and whispered simultaneous interpreting; and other elements such as stress-management training, d (Hale, 2007). The test design adopted here aims to address process-related skills and competences, heeding Hatim and Mason's (1997) warning that interpreting and translating testing run the danger of delivering just "once-off" demonstrations of talents that are otherwise procedure rather than product-related.

Two listening tests were administered. The first was a chat between two strangers who were having a casual talk on the street. The weather, everyday activities, and a description of the job of a travel agent are all discussed. The discourse was 350 words lengthy and lasted around 3 minutes. We informed test subjects that the hearing text would last a few minutes and that they would be needed to take notes in order to answer questions on the content of the listening text. Testees were permitted to know ahead of time the questions they would be given in regard to the two listening activities; however, answering the questions while listening to the listening exercises was actively discouraged.

The modest corpus of research on community interpreting training stems from an unfortunate overall lack of training available to or needed of interpreters. Pöchhacker bemoaned the poor pay and frequent lack of training for community interpreters, which has a corresponding effect on the attention and resources given to community interpreting by governmental or educational organisations. The lack of recognition and remuneration for interpreters, according to Hale, is a source of the lack of interest or funds available for training, resulting in a low demand for training courses and, as a result, a general scarcity of courses offered.

Conclusion

This article looked at the design and implementation of an intake test that was designed to elicit demonstrations of skill levels as well as information suggestive of skill levels that could not be directly assessed. This resulted in the creation of a large test with over 30 questions, tables, and exercises that took between 2 and 2.5 hours to complete. Often, only one of a trainee's two languages may be rigorously examined in community interpreter training; trainers can generally check performance in simulated or role-play exercises in just one language. As a result,

extensive questioning is not only permissible but also necessary to elicit skill capacities.

The test also included several questions designed to elicit replies concerning testees' grasp of the interpreting profession, as well as hypothetical scenarios that posed challenges to the interpreter's duty. These questions tried to ascertain testees' prior knowledge of interpreting and, indirectly, if they had attempted to learn anything about it in the absence of any (formal or informal) interpreting experience. Trainers observed that these questions had minimal influence on training content and trainee engagement at the intake level because the training itself included explanation and situation modelling of basic interpretation procedures and ideas, thus prior knowledge was neither required nor anticipated.

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